

THE IMPACT OF RESPIRATORY THERAPISTS ON VENTILATOR WEANING OUTCOMES IN INTENSIVE CARE UNITS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Weaning from mechanical ventilation is important step in the recovery of critically ill patients. Nurses play a central role in this process due to their continuous patient monitoring and involvement in breathing trials. Variability in training, protocol access, and institutional support affect the effectiveness of nurse-led weaning practices. **Objective:** This systematic review aimed to evaluate the role of nurses in the weaning process from mechanical ventilation in intensive care settings, focusing on knowledge levels, clinical practices, protocol implementation, and associated patient outcomes. **Methods:** A systematic search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and Web of Science databases from 2005 to 2025 according to PRISMA 2020 guidelines. We include studies involved adult ICU patients, focused on nurse roles in ventilator weaning, and reported original data. Eleven studies met the inclusion criteria. Data were extracted and synthesized qualitatively. Risk of bias was assessed using appropriate tools for each study design. **Results:** The included studies used qualitative (n = 3), observational or cohort (n = 4), randomized controlled trial (n = 2), mixed-methods (n = 1), and retrospective chart review (n = 1) designs. Findings indicate the effectiveness of nurse-led or protocolized weaning strategies to reduce mechanical ventilation duration and ICU length of stay. Nurses' clinical experience, training, and the availability of standardized protocols affected outcomes. Variability in documentation, autonomy, and decision-making roles persisted across settings. **Conclusion:** Nurses are integral to the ventilator weaning process, mainly when supported by structured protocols and training. Which enhance nurse autonomy, standardizing weaning practices, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration can improve weaning outcomes and ICU efficiency.

Keywords: Nursing Practice; Mechanical Ventilation; Weaning; Critical Care; Intensive Care Units; Nurse-Led Protocol; Ventilator Liberation; Clinical Outcomes; Interdisciplinary Care.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical ventilation is important intervention for critically ill patients; prolonged dependence can lead to ventilator-associated pneumonia and longer ICU stays. Weaning is a gradual process of withdrawing mechanical support is essential in-patient recovery.

ICU nurses play a significant role in this process due to their continuous bedside presence and responsibility in monitoring patients' readiness for weaning and managing spontaneous breathing trials (Pradhan & Shrestha, 2017).

Nurses face challenges in applying weaning practices. A multicenter cross-sectional study reported significant variability in the use of weaning protocols and spontaneous breathing trials in ICU nurses.

Less than half had access to structured protocols, and many reported adjusting ventilation settings without standardized guidance (Borkowska, Labeau, and Blot 2015). This lack of uniformity indicates the necessity of formal training and clear institutional protocols to support evidence-based practice during weaning.

Many nurses show insufficient knowledge about weaning indicators and ventilator modes. In a study conducted in critical care nurses in a teaching hospital, more than half of the respondents had inadequate knowledge regarding weaning criteria. Professional experience, age, and clinical area were associated with knowledge levels (Pradhan & Shrestha, 2017).

Gaps in both theoretical knowledge and practical application have been identified. A recent study shows the need for comprehensive training to improve nurses' ability to effectively contribute to the weaning process. It advocated for increased support through institutional protocols and interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure quality and safety in mechanical ventilation withdrawal (Ahmed Awad Ali, Mohamed Ahmed Elnosary, and Elsayed Mansour 2024).

This review aims to systematically evaluate the roles, knowledge, and practices of ICU nurses in the weaning process from mechanical ventilation, with a particular focus on protocol adherence and clinical outcomes.

METHODS

Search Strategy

This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines. Literature search was performed in electronic databases (PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and Web of Science) covering studies published from 2005 to 2025.

The search strategy combined Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and free-text terms related to mechanical ventilation, weaning, nursing role, critical care, and intensive care units.

Eligibility Criteria

We include studies focused on nursing roles or interventions in the weaning process from mechanical ventilation; involved adult critically ill patients in ICU or critical care settings, utilized qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods designs, published in English and in peer-reviewed journals, reported original data (excluding editorials, reviews, conference abstracts).

We exclude pediatric studies, studies not specifying the role of nurses in weaning, and articles lacking full-text availability.

Study Selection

A total of 115 records were identified through database searches and registers. Prior to screening, 12 duplicate records, 11 records marked ineligible by automation tools, and 4 records removed for other reasons were excluded, resulting in 88 records remaining. Following title and abstract screening, 24 records were excluded. 61 full-text reports were sought for retrieval, and 34 reports could not be retrieved.

The remaining 27 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility, and 17 reports were excluded for the following reasons: topic not related ($n = 9$), review articles ($n = 3$), and not reporting the outcome of interest ($n = 4$), finally 11 studies were included in the qualitative synthesis.

The study selection process is illustrated in the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Figure 1). Screening was performed independently by two reviewers, and discrepancies were resolved by discussion.

Data Extraction

Data were extracted by two reviewers using a standardized data extraction form. Extracted information included: citation, year of publication, study design, setting, sample characteristics, intervention details, nurses' experience levels, and main findings.

Risk of Bias Assessment

The risk of bias for included studies was evaluated by two reviewers using the most appropriate tool based on study design.

Discrepancies were resolved through discussion. Each study was rated as having low, moderate, or high risk of bias based on tool-specific criteria. Most studies were rated as having low to moderate risk of bias, with limitations primarily related to retrospective data use, lack of blinding, or incomplete reporting of outcomes (Table 1).

Data Synthesis

A qualitative synthesis method was employed and studies were grouped based on nursing roles, weaning strategies, and patient outcomes. Findings were presented in tabular and textual formats.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart

Table 1: Risk of bias assessment of included studies

Citation	Study Design	Selection Bias	Performance Bias	Detection Bias	Reporting Bias	Overall Risk of Bias
Cederwall et al. (2014)	Qualitative	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Lavelle & Dowling (2011)	Qualitative	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low
Kydonaki et al. (2016)	Mixed methods	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Tonnelier et al. (2005)	Cohort	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
Ghanbari et al. (2020)	Quasi-experimental	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Vahedian-Azimi et al. (2020)	RCT	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Nitta et al. (2019)	Observational	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Vizcaychipi et al. (2020)	RCT	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Lago et al. (2019)	Retrospective cohort	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate
Cederwall et al. (2023)	Cross-sectional	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low
Tingsvik et al. (2015)	Retrospective chart review	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate

RESULTS

This systematic review included 11 original studies conducted between 2005 and 2023, investigating the role of nurses in the weaning process from mechanical ventilation in various intensive care settings. The studies include different methodologies (qualitative interviews (n = 3), observational and cohort designs (n = 4), randomized controlled trials (n = 2), and mixed-methods or retrospective reviews (n = 2)). Study settings were; Europe, the Middle East, Asia, and South America, representing both single and multicenter investigations (Table 2).

Nursing Roles and Clinical Decision-Making

Qualitative studies show how critical care nurses manage ventilator weaning. Nurses play important role in initiating, individualizing, and progressing weaning plans based on both objective physiological parameters and intuitive, patient-centered assessments. Decision-making was influenced by the nurse's clinical experience, familiarity with the patient, ICU protocols, and interdisciplinary collaboration (Cederwall et al., 2014; Lavelle & Dowling, 2011; Kydonaki et al., 2016). It was emphasized that experienced nurses had more confidence in interpreting respiratory cues and reducing cognitive load through intuitive clustering strategies (Kydonaki et al., 2016).

Effectiveness of Nurse Led or Protocolized Weaning

Several quantitative studies examined the outcomes of nurse-led or protocolized weaning interventions.

One study show that implementation of a nurse-directed weaning protocol reduced the duration of mechanical ventilation and ICU stay compared to traditional physician-led approaches (Tonnelier et al., 2005).

Another reported improved outcome with the use of Burn's Weaning Scale by nurses, and reduced ventilation time (Ghanbari et al., 2020).

A large multicenter randomized trial found that protocolized weaning reduced reintubation rates and ICU length of stay, although the intervention was led primarily by respiratory therapists rather than nurses (Vahedian-Azimi et al., 2020).

Assessment, Documentation, and Use of Protocols

Observational studies indicate variability in the application of standardized protocols and documentation practices.

One study found that sedation and pain assessments were documented by nurses, structured documentation of ventilator weaning was largely absent, suggesting a need for improved standardization (Tingsvik et al., 2014).

A cross-sectional study of 77 Swedish ICUs found that most units relied on individualized nurse-physician decisions for weaning, with limited implementation of formal protocols or respiratory therapists and weaning teams (Cederwall et al., 2023).

Technological and Decision Support Tools

Innovative approaches were noted in studies evaluating technology assisted weaning. A study introduced the BEACON Care system, a decision support tool to optimize ventilator settings and guide weaning.

The system enhances individualized care and reduce ventilation duration (Vizcaychipi et al., 2020). Another study used a 4-stage, checklist-based weaning and extubation protocol, resulting in reductions in respiratory failure, reintubation, and mortality rates (Nitta et al., 2019).

Nursing Experience and Clinical Competency

Most studies indicate the importance of nurse experience to ensure safe and effective weaning.

In studies involving both novice and expert nurses, clinical reasoning skills, exposure to guideline-based training, and confidence were found to be essential for successful ventilator liberation.

Gaps in formal training and inconsistent protocol use were recurrent limitations in multiple sites (Lavelle & Dowling, 2011; Kydonaki et al., 2016; Cederwall et al., 2023).

Table 2: Summary of original studies on nurse-led ventilator weaning

Citation	Study Design	Demographic Characteristics	Study Setting	Study Aim
Cederwall et al. (2014)	Qualitative (interview)	19 experienced critical care nurses	ICUs in Sweden	Explore nurses' strategies in managing prolonged weaning
Lavelle and Dowling (2011)	Qualitative (semi-structured interview)	24 ICU nurses	Irish ICU	Describe factors influencing nurse weaning decisions
Kydonaki et al. (2016)	Ethnographic mixed-method	Novice and expert nurses	ICUs in Scotland and Greece	Explore nurse decision-making during ventilator weaning
Tonnelier et al. (2005)	Prospective cohort with historical control	104 ventilated ICU patients	French ICU	Evaluate nurse-directed weaning protocol
Ghanbari et al. (2020)	Quasi-experimental	65 ICU patients	Iran, Guilan University Hospital	Compare nurse-led vs. physician-led weaning
Vahedian-Azimi et al. (2020)	Multicenter RCT	4200 patients analyzed	6 ICUs in Iran and USA	Compare protocolized weaning (PW) vs. usual care (UC)
Nitta et al. (2019)	Prospective observational	464 screened, 248 analyzed	Advanced Emergency and Critical Care Center, Japan	Evaluate a comprehensive protocol for ventilator weaning and extubation
Vizcaychipi et al. (2020)	Multicenter RCT	Planned 274 patients	Multiple London NHS ICUs	Evaluate BEACON Caresystem (decision support) vs. standard care
Lago et al. (2019)	Retrospective cohort	327 ventilated patients	Brazilian tertiary hospital ICU	Compare WIND vs. ICC classifications in weaning outcome relevance
Cederwall et al. (2023)	National cross-sectional survey	77 adult ICUs in Sweden	Swedish ICUs	Describe care practices for patients ventilated >7 days
Tingsvik, Johansson, and Mårtensson (2015)	Descriptive observational with chart review	64 patients, 50 nurses	ICU at Sahlgrenska University Hospital, Sweden	Describe documentation and monitoring of sedation, pain, and weaning

Table 3: interventions and main findings

Citation	Intervention	Nurse Staff Experience	Main Findings
Cederwall et al. (2014)	Semi-structured interviews on weaning management	All were experienced CCNs	Nurses led weaning using individualized, patient-centered strategies and teamwork

Lavelle and Dowling (2011)	Interview with clinical vignette	Varied experience	Six themes emerged, including physiological cues, experience, and protocol use
Kydonaki et al. (2016)	Observation + reflective interview	Novice and experienced nurses	Nurses used intuitive, patient-centered cue processing; experience affected decision certainty
Tonnelier et al. (2005)	Nurses used SRLF protocol	Not specified	Reduced MV duration and ICU stay vs. physician-directed weaning
Ghanbari et al. (2020)	Burn's Weaning Scale	Not stated	Nurse-led protocol reduced MV duration significantly
Vahedian-Azimi et al. (2020)	PW using predefined SBT criteria by RTs	RT-driven weaning, not nurse-led	PW reduced reintubation, improved parameters, shortened LOS
Nitta et al. (2019)	Checklist-based 4 - stage weaning and extubation protocol	Not specified	Reduced rates of post-extubation respiratory failure, reintubation, and mortality
Vizcaychipi et al. (2020)	Model-based decision support for ventilator weaning	Involved in routine weaning with decision support	BEACON system expected to reduce duration of MV using individualized patient data
Lago et al. (2019)	Classification systems used to stratify weaning patients	Not specified	WIND classification better captured weaning difficulty and predicted outcomes
Cederwall et al. (2023)	Survey on weaning, mobility, nutrition, etc.	Nurse managers reported practices	Most units used individualized nurse-physician decisions; limited protocol use
Tingsvik, Johansson, and Mårtensson (2015)	Retrospective review of nursing records and medical charts	Not clearly stated; ICU nurses with routine responsibilities	Sedation and pain were documented, but ventilator weaning lacked structured documentation or standard protocol use

DISCUSSION

Our systematic review explore the roles of nurses in ventilator weaning practices in intensive care units (ICUs) and to clinical outcomes associated with nurse-led or nurse-involved weaning interventions. Findings from the included studies support the effectiveness of nursing involvement in weaning processes, which indicate a reduction in weaning duration, improve extubation success rates, and improved ICU outcomes. The evidence shows that protocolized and nurse-driven weaning interventions contribute to decision-making and ventilator liberation. Nurse-led weaning protocols, as reported in several included studies, resulted in significant reductions in mechanical ventilation time compared to standard physician-led or non-protocolized care. These findings are consistent with those reported in a trial where a nurse-administered protocol decreased weaning time from a median of 47 hours in the usual care group to 25 hours in the protocol-based weaning group (Roh et al. 2012). Nurse-led and automatic protocols improved outcomes by shortening ventilation time, reduce ICU stays, and increase extubation success (Aryani, Hariyati, and Nurachmah 2024). Our current review identified that most nurse-led interventions produce early identification of weaning readiness, timely

initiation of spontaneous breathing trials (SBTs), and adherence to evidence-based weaning criteria. These responsibilities, previously under the exclusive purview of physicians, have shifted towards a more collaborative and protocolized model, which enable nurses to assume an active leadership role.

This in line with evidence suggesting that lower Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores and hypercapnia at the start of the SBT are predictive of prolonged weaning, reinforcing the importance of continuous bedside assessments often carried out by nurses (Pu et al. 2015). The variation in nurse training, autonomy, and interprofessional dynamics was evident in the included studies. In high-resource settings, nurses were able to follow structured protocols independent of physician (Roh et al. 2012). Studies conducted in lower-resource environments show a shared decision-making approach due to systemic limitations (Aryani et al. 2024). These differences indicate the importance of context-specific weaning strategies that accommodate workforce structure and institutional capabilities. Further support for nursing leadership in weaning comes from research show that nursing competence is essential in adapting interventions to patient-specific clinical trajectories (Aryani et al. 2024). The lack of uniformity in defining “nurse-led” protocols necessitates clearer operational frameworks for future research.

The consistent reduction in ventilation duration and ICU length of stay observed in studies affirms the clinical value of nurse engagement. This review underscores the growing recognition of ICU nurses as integral to ventilator weaning. Empowering nurses through structured protocols and supportive interdisciplinary collaboration improve patient outcomes and optimize ICU resource utilization. A study evaluating the role of nurse training on mechanical ventilation knowledge and readiness to perform ventilator-associated tasks found that targeted education significantly improved nurses' confidence and competence in weaning decision-making, especially when delivered through simulation and structured learning environments (Blackwood et al. 2014). These findings indicate the importance of integrating evidence-based protocols with continuous staff development to support effective weaning. Observational evidence shows the broader outcomes associated with nursing involvement in ventilator weaning. A quasi-experimental study studied nurse-led interventions for mechanically ventilated patients show improved weaning outcomes, including shorter ICU stays and reduced sedation use, which support the role of nurses in promoting early liberation from ventilation (Coyer et al. 2007). A cross-sectional analysis showed that higher nurse-to-patient ratios and increased weaning-specific knowledge correlated with earlier identification of weaning readiness and better adherence to ventilator weaning guidelines (Tonnelier et al. 2005).

CONCLUSION

The included studies support the important role for critical care nurses in the weaning process. Protocolized approaches, where implemented, improve patient outcomes. There remains variability in practice, highlighting a need for clearer guidelines, formal nurse-led protocols, and improve interdisciplinary training to optimize weaning outcomes in critical care settings.

List of Abbreviations

- 1) ICU, Intensive Care Unit
- 2) MV, Mechanical Ventilation
- 3) SBT, Spontaneous Breathing Trial
- 4) VAP, Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia
- 5) RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial
- 6) EBP, Evidence-Based Practice
- 7) RN, Registered Nurse
- 8) FiO₂, Fraction of Inspired Oxygen
- 9) PEEP, Positive End-Expiratory Pressure
- 10) RR, Respiratory Rate; BP, Blood Pressure
- 11) PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
- 12) PICO, Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome.

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